

**Prof. Georgi Georgiev, DVSci: SCIENTIFIC RISK ASSESSMENT OF
OCCURRENCE AND SPREAD OF RHINOPNEUMONITIS IN HORSES WITH
DEVELOPMENT OF SEVERE NEUROLOGICAL CLINICS AND
MYELOENCEPHALOPATHYES**

(SUMMARY)

The Rhinopneumonitis in horses is an acute viral disease, manifested by abortions in late stages of pregnancy and severe lung damage in both one-year-old and adult horses. The disease is characterized by very variable clinics with appearance of vesicles on the hairless parts of the body, respiratory symptoms, abortions in the last third of pregnancy, and the birth of non-life offspring to nervous signs - paresis and paralysis. The infection is associated with 2 equine (herpes) alpha herpesviruses - herpesvirus-1 and - 4 (Equine Herpes Virus - EHV-1 and EHV-4). The frequent appearance of a clinic with nervous signs in recent years is characteristic of infections caused by herpes viruses. In addition to the major role of EHV-1, serotype 4 and, in rare cases, serotype 3 viruses may be involved.

Herpesvirus virus 1 infection in horses (EHV-1) is responsible for the occurrence of upper respiratory tract infections in young animals and abortions in pregnant mares in late pregnancy. The other serotype of equine herpesvirus 4 (EHV-4) was until recently considered a subtype of EHV-1, but through the use of molecular techniques to characterize the genome, it is now a separate viral species and is responsible for upper respiratory tract infection in young horses. Both viruses are able to induce brain disease accompanied by myeloencephalopathy, although EHV-1 is clearly the more common cause of this form of the disease.

According to official data of the International Equestrian Federation (FEI) in February 2021, in Valencia, Spain, a neurological form of rhinopneumonitis caused by EHV-1 was confirmed. This is probably the most serious outbreak of EHV-1 in Europe in decades, affecting more than 752 horses with 18 deaths to date.

According to information from the World organization of animal health (OIE), a number of EU countries have reported the presence of a neurological form of rhinopneumonitis in horses and a disease with myoencephalomyelitis in recent years, and data for Bulgaria are scarce or no such information is available.

These facts led us to make a scientific assessment of the risk of the occurrence and spread of rhinopneumonitis in horses based on the availability of evidence of increased circulation of EHV-1 in Europe, the development of severe neurological clinics accompanied by myeloencephalopathy and to propose adequate measures against this disease.